

Depletion Time Interval Optimization Algorithm Based on Monte Carlo Perturbation Technique and Their Application to Depletion Benchmarks

Ho Jin Park ^{1,*}

¹Kyung Hee Univerisity, Deogyong-daero 1732, Yongin-si, Gyeonggi-do, Korea

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803231

ABSTRACT

A new concept of depletion time interval optimization has been developed using the Monte Carlo (MC) perturbation technique. The proposed algorithm quantifies reactivity errors induced by temporal changes in one-group reaction rates during depletion and adaptively determines optimal depletion time intervals that satisfy a prescribed convergence criterion. The method combines MC perturbation calculations, which estimate the sensitivity of reactivity to number-density variations, with a direct-subtraction approach that evaluates number-density changes caused by reaction-rate perturbations. The resulting algorithm automatically adjusts depletion intervals so that the reactivity variation between steps remains within a user-defined tolerance. The methodology was verified using a simple UO₂ fuel pin benchmark with the McCARD code. The optimized depletion time steps were compared with conventional, uniformly divided time intervals, and the results demonstrated that the proposed method provides comparable or improved accuracy with significantly fewer burnup steps. In particular, the root-mean-square (RMS) reactivity error decreased as the convergence criterion was tightened, confirming the consistency of the approach. This study shows that the proposed algorithm efficiently and autonomously determines optimized depletion intervals.

Keywords: Monte Carlo Depletion, Depletion Time interval, Optimization, Perturbation, McCARD

1. INTRODUCTION

In nuclear core design analyses, the general neutron transport equation is commonly formulated as a function of six or seven phase parameters (i.e., position, energy, direction, and time). To improve computational efficiency, the time domain is typically categorized into three types of analyses: steady-state, transient, and depletion calculations. In the depletion analysis, the nuclide number densities are updated at each depletion time step (DTS) according to the Bateman or depletion equations, which represents a balance equation for nuclear reactions and decays. Accordingly, the depletion time discretization is essential to solve the depletion equation. Basically, finer discretization of depletion time intervals reduces errors but increases the computational burden. In general, these depletion time intervals are manually determined by the code user based on experience. Typically, a user specifies finer depletion time steps to capture the transient behavior of poison nuclides such as Xenon and Samarium, as well as the depletion of burnable absorber nuclides like gadolinium. As the end of the cycle approaches, however, the depletion time intervals are provided more sparsely. However, it is highly challenging for a user to determine appropriate depletion time intervals for a new system.

There are a few studies on the topics to optimize depletion time steps or to enhance burnup analysis capabilities. W. Yang developed a linear time-dependent flux approximation for nuclide depletion based on a perturbation method. [1] In this method, a perturbation method is employed to derive the

*parkhj@khu.ac.kr.

first-order expansion of the time-dependent flux. Pusa et al. [2] reviewed matrix exponential methods for solving burnup equations and demonstrates through test cases that the Chebyshev rational approximation method (CRAM) provides a robust and accurate solution with very short computation time. Meanwhile, Park et al. [3] confirmed that the finer the division of depletion time intervals, the smaller the impact of reactivity error propagation in burnup analyses. In particular, they confirmed that such burnup errors arise because the changes in one-group reaction rates, which are used to solve the depletion equations, are not properly accounted for over intervals in which the reaction rates change. In this paper, a new concept of depletion time interval optimization based on perturbation method will be introduced for efficient MC burnup analyses.

2. OPTIMIZATION OF DEPLETION TIME INTERVAL BY MONTE CARLO PERTURBTION TECHNIQUE

2.1. Origins of Reactivity Errors in Depletion Analysis

In depletion analysis, the operation period of the nuclear system is discretized into non-overlapping depletion time steps (DTS), where n represents the index of each depletion interval. The change in the number density of nuclide i in cell m ($N_{m,i}$) of the operating nuclear system during DTS n can be determined by solving the Bateman or depletion equation;

$$\frac{dN_{m,i}(t)}{dt} = \sum_j l_{ij} \lambda_j N_{m,j}(t) + \sum_j \gamma_{m,ij}^n N_{m,j}(t) - (\lambda_i + \gamma_{m,i}^n) N_{m,i}(t), \quad t \in [t_n, t_{n+1}], \quad N_{m,i}^n = N_{m,i}(t_n), \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma_{m,i}^n$ is a one-group microscopic absorption reaction rate of nuclide i in cell m and $\gamma_{m,ij}^n$ is the fraction of the one-group microscopic reaction rate of nuclide j in cell m which leads to the creation of nuclide i . The remaining symbols are defined according to the usual convention.

Figure 1. Comparison of one-group reaction rates of a typical PWR single pin problem over burnup.

This depletion equation determines the number densities at the $(n+1)^{\text{th}}$ DTS based on the number densities and reaction rate information obtained at the n^{th} DTS. It should be noted that, between the n^{th} DTS and $(n+1)^{\text{th}}$ DTS, the decay constants and fission yield are typically treated as constant, whereas

the one group microscopic reaction rates change over time. However, because the depletion equation assumes that the one-group reaction rates remain constant during this interval, this approximation may lead to the errors in the number densities at the $(n+1)^{\text{th}}$ DTS.

Figure 1 compares one-group absorption reaction rates of major actinide nuclides (i.e. ^{235}U , ^{238}U , ^{239}Pu , and ^{240}Pu) in a PWR single pin problem over burnup. It can be inferred that the variation of reaction rate curves over burnup may affect the depletion calculation results due to such temporal discretization. Furthermore, it is evident that the depletion time interval should be refined as much as possible to minimize these errors.

2.2. Optimization of Depletion Time Intervals

In this study, a new concept of optimized depletion time intervals is introduced by considering the origins of error in reactivity over burnup. Let us denote the one-group reaction rates at the previous and current DTS as $R(t_0)$ and $R(t_1)$, respectively, and consider the next DTS to be arbitrarily set as $t_1 + \Delta t$. And the one-group reaction rate at this next DTS, $R(t_1 + \Delta t)$ can then be predicted using a linear extrapolation. The objective of this algorithm is to ensure that the resulting change in reactivity, due to variations in the reaction rates, remains within a prescribed tolerance ε .

Figure 2. Reaction rates estimations by linear extrapolation for a next depletion time step(t_2).

To quantify the change in reactivity, ΔR , due to change of reaction rates, the MC perturbation technique and direct subtraction [4] were used in this approach. Firstly, the direct subtraction method captures the resulting changes in number densities due to variations in reaction rates, $\partial N/\partial R$, as expressed by the equation below.

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial R} \cong \frac{N(R + \Delta R) - N(R)}{\Delta R} \quad (2)$$

Meanwhile, the MC perturbation technique determines the corresponding changes in reactivity arising from variations in the number densities, $\partial \rho/\partial N$. Consequently, the overall change in reactivity resulting from a change in reaction rate can be expressed as:

$$\Delta \rho(t_n) = \sum_{i,\alpha} \left| \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial N_i} \cdot \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial R_{\alpha,i}} \cdot (R_{\alpha,i}(t_n + \Delta t) - R_{\alpha,i}(t_n)) \right|, \quad (3)$$

where $R_{\alpha,i}$ denotes the one-group α -type microscopic reaction rate for i -isotope.

$$\Delta \rho(t_n) < \varepsilon. \quad (4)$$

When the change in reactivity, $\Delta\rho$, satisfies the convergence criterion ε as shown in Eq. (4), the current time step Δt is accepted as the next discrete time step, t_{n+1} . If convergence is not achieved, Δt is reduced by Δt_{itv} , and the procedure returns to the step of calculating $\Delta\rho$ using Eq. (3). Figure 2 illustrates the algorithm for the burnup interval optimization method based on the MC perturbation technique. It should be noted that the inclusion of perturbation-based computations in this optimization procedure can lead to a significant increase in computational cost. In Eq. (3), the inter-nuclide interference effects in $\partial N/\partial R$ are assumed to be negligible and are therefore ignored. For example, the change in the number density of the j -th nuclide induced by the reaction rate of the i -th nuclide is approximated as zero.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS FOR DEPLETION TIME INTERVAL OPTIMIZATION METHOD

3.1. UO₂ Pin Depletion Problem and Calculation Condition

To evaluate the proposed depletion time interval optimization concept, a typical UO₂ pin problem from the VERA benchmark problem [5] was analyzed using the McCARD Monte Carlo code [5]. Table I summarizes the geometrical and material specifications for the VERA 1C pin depletion problem. In this study, all burnup calculations were performed using a constant extrapolation at the predictor stage and a backward extrapolation at the corrector stage (CEBE), implemented within the matrix exponential method (MEM) solver for the depletion equations.

Table I. Specification of a typical UO₂ pin problem from VERA depletion benchmark.

Region	Parameter	Value
UO ₂ Fuel	Pellet Radius (cm)	0.4096
	²³⁵ U enrichment (wt.%)	3.1
	Density (g/cm ³)	10.2570
	Temperature (Kelvin)	900
Zr Cladding	Inner Radius (cm)	0.4180
	Outer Radius (cm)	0.4750
	Density (g/cm ³)	6.5600
	Temperature (Kelvin)	600
H ₂ O Moderator	Density (g/cm ³)	0.700
	Temperature (Kelvin)	600
Power Density (w/gU)		40.00
Pin Pitch (cm)		1.2600

To obtain the reference solution of reactivities for the pin depletion analysis, McCARD depletion calculations were conducted using the CEBE/MEM scheme, varying the number of discrete time steps (DTSs) as 22, 40, 123, 242, 520, and 1200. The corresponding burnup intervals near the EOC for MEM22, MEM40, MEM520, and MEM1200 are approximately 5, 2.5, 0.125, and 0.05 MWd/kgU, respectively. The calculation using the MEM solver with 1200 DTS (hereafter referred to as MEM1200) was taken as the reference result for comparison. Table II summarizes the root mean square (RMS) errors and k_{int} values at a burnup of 60 MWd/kgU for each case. Noted that the reactivity difference between MEM1200 and the other cases decreases with an increasing number of DTSs. It can be observed that MEM520 achieved full convergence, considering the statistical uncertainty (<30 pcm).

Table II. Comparison of RMS errors in reactivity and k_{inf} at end of cycle (EOC, 60 MWd/kgU) for a typical UO₂ pin problem as a function of the number of depletion time steps.

Case	Number of DTS (#)	Burnup interval near EOC (MWd/kgU)	RMS error in reactivity (pcm)	k_{inf} (at EOC)
MEM22	22	5	157	0.79210
MEM40	40	2.5	129	0.79305
MEM123	123	0.5	84	0.79559
MEM242	242	0.25	64	0.79524
MEM310	310	0.25	43	0.79513
MEM520	520	0.125	45	0.79497
MEM1200	1200	0.05	-	0.79559

* The statistical uncertainty (1σ) of k_{inf} is less than 30 pcm, and the RMS error (2σ) is within 12 pcm

3.2. Application of the Depletion Time Interval Optimization Algorithm for UO₂ Pin Depletion Problem

The optimized DTSs for the pin problem were determined using the depletion time interval optimization algorithm based on the MC perturbation technique as mentioned in Section 2.2. Table III presents the optimized DTS results corresponding to the convergence parameters (i.e., ϵ and Δt_{itv}) for the pin problem. As described in the previous section, Δt_{itv} denotes the time interval reduction applied to the previous step when the calculated $\Delta\rho$ under the current conditions does not satisfy the convergence criterion ϵ . The Δt_{max} parameter represents the initial time interval for the next burnup calculation, which was set to 100 effective full-power days (EFPD) in all cases. In this study, two uranium and two plutonium nuclides (i.e. ²³⁵U, ²³⁸U, ²³⁹Pu, and ²⁴⁰Pu) were considered for the depletion time interval optimization algorithm.

Table III. DTS results determined by the depletion time interval optimization algorithm for a UO₂ pin problem.

Case	ϵ (pcm)	Δt_{itv} (EFPD)	Δt_{max} (EFPD)	DTS
I	10			240
II	20			103
III	30	3	100	69
IV	40			53
V	50			44

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the number of burnup points per interval between the reference and optimized time steps with a similar total number of burnup points. In the reference case, the burnup range is divided into equal intervals; therefore, the number of burnup points in each interval is nearly uniform. For example, in MEM242, the number of time steps in the 10 MWd/kgU interval is $242/6 \approx 40$, whereas in MEM123, $123/6 \approx 20$ DTSs are assigned to each interval. In the depletion time interval optimization algorithm, the changes of one-group reaction rates shown in Figure 1 is considered, and relatively more depletion time steps (DTSs) are allocated in the 0–10 MWd/kgU and 20–30 MWd/kgU burnup intervals. The optimization considers the changes of ²³⁵U one-group reaction rates in the 0–10 MWd/kgU burnup range and the changes of plutonium one-group reaction rates in the 20–30 MWd/kgU range.

Figure 3. Distribution of the number of DTS (depletion time step) per interval between the reference and optimized time steps with comparable total burnup points.
(Left : MEM242 vs Case I, Right : MEM123 vs CaseII)

Table IV compares the RMS errors in reactivity and k_{inf} values at the EOC for five optimized cases and reference (MEM1200). From the results of Cases V through I, it is observed that the RMS error of reactivity decreases as the convergence criterion ϵ becomes smaller. In the MEM242 case, where the burnup steps were evenly divided, the RMS error was 64 pcm, whereas in Case I with a similar number of burnup steps (=240) gives a smaller RMS error of 52 pcm was calculated. Moreover, the proposed burnup interval optimization algorithm demonstrated a burnup accuracy similar to Case II, which used 103 burnup steps, compared to MEM123, which employed 123 equally divided burnup intervals. From the results, it was noted that the algorithm has been demonstrated to efficiently and automatically optimize the burnup intervals.

Table IV. RMS errors in reactivity and k_{inf} at end of cycle (EOC, 60 MWd/kgU) for each optimized DTS case.

Case	ϵ (pcm)	DTS	RMS error in reactivity (pcm)	k_{inf} (at EOC)
I	10	240	52	0.79584
II	20	103	60	0.79486
III	30	69	139	0.79319
IV	40	53	184	0.79339
V	50	44	190	0.79302
MEM1200 (Reference)		1200	-	0.79559

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a new concept of depletion time interval optimization algorithm was proposed using the reaction rate and number density perturbation calculations. This algorithm uses the MC perturbation technique in MC simulations and direct subtraction method in depletion analysis to quantify the error in reactivity due to the changes in one-group reaction rates over burnup. Through verification and validation using the simple UO_2 pin problem, it was confirmed that the newly proposed methodology can accurately predict the optimized depletion time intervals.

In near future, its applicability will also be examined for problems involving burnable absorber nuclides (e.g., Gd_2O_3). In addition, for the practical application of this algorithm, various sensitivity analyses are

required to comprehensively determine the recommended values of key parameters (particularly the convergence criterion, ϵ).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) grant funded by the Korea government (MSIT) (No. RS-2025-13222972).

REFERENCES

- [1] W. S. Yang and T. J. Downer. "A Linear Time-Dependent Flux Approximation for Nuclide Depletion Based On A Perturbation Method.", *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **17**, pp. 37-42 (1990). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/030645499090063>.
- [2] M. Pusa and Jaakko Leppänen. "Computing the Matrix Exponential in Burnup Calculations." *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **164**, pp. 140-150 (2010). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE09-14>.
- [3] H. J. Park et al. "Monte Carlo Burnup and its Uncertainty Propagation Analyses for VERA Depletion Benchmarks by McCARD." *Nucl. Eng. Technol.*, **50**, pp. 1043-1050 (2018). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1738573318301335>.
- [4] H. J. Park, H. J. Shim, and C. H. Kim. "Uncertainty Propagation in Monte Carlo Depletion Analysis." *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **167**, pp. 196-208 (2011). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE09-106>.
- [5] K.S. Kim. "Specifications for the VERA Depletion Benchmark Suite." CASL-U-2015-PHI.VCS.P11.02-010, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (2015).
- [6] H. J. Shim et al. "McCARD: Monte Carlo Code for Advanced Reactor Design and Analysis." *Nucl. Eng. Technol.*, **44**, pp.151-176 (2012).